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The Solidity of the World Banking System

Bank Capital to Asset Ratio-BCAR increased by 7.97% between 2010 and 2021

The World Bank calculates the Bank Capital to Asset Ratio-BCAR. BCAR is the ratio of the sum of bank capital and reserves to total assets. Capital and reserves include funds contributed by owners, retained earnings, general and special reserves, provisions, and value adjustments. Capital includes tier 1 capital (paid-up shares and common stock), which is a common feature in banking systems across countries, and total regulatory capital, which includes several specific types of subordinated debt instruments that do not have to be repaid whether funds are needed to maintain minimum capital levels (these include tier 2 capital and tier 3 capital). Total assets include all non-financial and financial assets. It is therefore a measure that takes into consideration the ability of banks to cope with investments. We must consider that not all countries have complete time series. Therefore, we will consider only a part of the countries, i.e. those for which there is a complete time series between 2010 and 2021.

Ranking of countries for BCAR in 2021. Paraguay ranks first by value of BCAR in 2021 with a value of 69.10%, followed by Tajikistan with a value of 20.92%, Uganda with 14.66% , from Cambodia with a value of 14.44%, and from the Central African Republic with a value of 13.85%. In the middle of the table are Mauritius with a value of 9.11%, followed by Ghana with an amount of 9.01%, Latvia with 8.97%, El Salvador with 8.90% and Albania with 8.85%. Chad closes the ranking with a value of 4.99%, followed by Denmark with a value of 4.79%, Canada with a value of 4.775, Macao with 2.84% and Equatorial Guinea with a value by 1.32%.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in BCAR value between 2010 and 2021. Paraguay ranks first in value of percentage change in BCAR value with an amount of 1,090.89%, followed by Nigeria with an amount of 353.53%, Congo with a value of 123.16%, Lesotho with a value of 105.47%, Argentina with a value of 79.46%. In the middle of the table are Uzbekistan with an amount of 6.38%, followed by Kosovo with 6.06%, Kuwait with an amount of 5.99%, and Bulgaria with an amount of 5.97%, and from the Slovak Republic with an amount of 5.53%. Croatia closes the ranking with a value of -41.96%, followed by Ukraine with a value of -44.42%, San Marino with a value of -45.90%, Lithuania with a value of -83.81%, from Equatorial Guinea with -116.03%. Between 2010 and 2021, the average value of the BCAR increased by 7.97% on average.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with Silhouette coefficient eliminating outliers. Below we consider the clustering achieved with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient by eliminating the outliers. The elimination of the outliers was necessary due to the presence of Paraguay which has a very high BCAR value, i.e. equal to an amount of 69.10% in 2021. Two clusters are therefore identified, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Albania, Congo, Mauritius, Costa Rica, Cyprus, Lesotho, Chad, Madagascar, Chile, Gabon, Nicaragua, Seychelles, San Marino, Slovak Republic, Korea Rep., Macao, South Africa, Bolivia, Vietnam, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Cameroon, Czechia, Israel, Malta,

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Canada, Guatemala, Finland, Portugal, Denmark, France, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Belgium, Italy, Germany, Australia;

- *Cluster 2*: Kuwait, Trinidad and Tobago, Bulgaria, Turkey, Belarus, Ecuador, Panama, Tanzania, Kenya, Bosnia and Herzegovina, United Arab Emirates, Uganda, North Macedonia, Solomon Islands, Georgia, Honduras, Ghana, Papua New Guinea, Moldova, Saudi Arabia, Zambia, Kosovo, Kyrgyz Republic, West Bank and Gaza, Indonesia, Estonia, El Salvador, Angola, Uzbekistan, Brunei Darussalam, Fiji, Ireland, Hungary, Colombia, Slovenia, Brazil, Mexico, United States, Latvia, Peru, Russian Federation, Montenegro, Philippines, Namibia, Argentina, Malaysia, Ukraine, Poland.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that the value of cluster 2 exceeds the value of Cluster 1, i.e. $C2=10.33 > C1=6.72$. From a geographical point of view, we note that the Western world, i.e. Europe, Canada and Australia, have reduced BCAR values compared to the countries of South East Asia, Central Africa, Central and South America and the United States. It must be considered that the banking system of Western countries tends to be more exposed to the dimension of risks compared to the countries of the South of the World. In fact, Western countries use the banking system and also the financial system to bear the risks of investments in technological innovation and research and development. These are particularly risky investments characterized by a high level of failure, especially in the case of start-ups. We can note that one of the few Western countries with medium-high values in terms of BCAR is Ireland. The United States are also an exception in that they can count on a Central Bank, i.e. the Federal Reserve Bank-FED, which is certainly a leader among Central Banks worldwide. From clustering, therefore, a condition of difficulty for the European banking system appears evident, which is particularly serious especially considering that in Europe the banking system also carries out part of the activity carried out by the financial markets in the USA. In the analysis we considered a historical series between 2010 and 2021. However, there are doubts that the condition of Russia can still be positive especially following the invasion of Ukraine.

Conclusions. The solidity of the banking system is necessary to allow the economy of a country to be able to withstand economic crises and to cope with the uncertainties of the financial system. Furthermore, the stability of the banking system is also a determinant capable of measuring the banks' ability to efficiently internalize the risks present in the market. There are some countries that have grown in terms of BCAR such as Paraguay, Nigeria, and Congo. However, it must be considered that this strengthening of the BCAR is also due to the adoption of prudent banking management models which tend to increase the stability of the banks. The analysis shows that the European banking system has less efficient levels of stability than the US one, raising the question of the effectiveness of the ECB economic policies compared to the FED ones.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

